

THE METHODS OF PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT IN SCHOOLS

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Abstract. Personnel management in the field of education plays a key role in ensuring a high-quality educational process and the successful functioning of the school. Effective management of the teaching staff contributes not only to improving the professional level of teachers, but also to creating a favorable working atmosphere conducive to the development of students. In this article, it will be considered the main methods of personnel management in schools, which help heads of educational institutions to effectively coordinate the activities of teachers and ensure a high level of the educational process.

Keywords: Professional competence, motivation, leadership, communication, educational environment, staff training and development, staff satisfaction.

Personnel management in schools is a process focused on the effective management of the human resources of an educational institution in order to achieve educational goals, ensure the quality of education and create a favorable working atmosphere. It includes the planning, organization, management, coordination and control of the activities of the staff of the educational institution [4]. The purpose of personnel management in schools is to ensure the effective use of human resources, create conditions for professional growth and development of employees, increase their motivation and work efficiency, as well as ensure the fulfillment of educational tasks. Human resources management in schools includes a wide range of activities, ranging from planning human resources and hiring new employees to motivation, training, evaluation and staff development. This process is aimed at creating conditions for the effective functioning of the school, improving the quality of education, and developing professional

Human resources management in the educational field plays a crucial role in providing quality education for students. The strategies and methods used by school administrators are aimed at developing professionalism, motivation, communication, taking into account individual needs, evaluating productivity and creating a favorable working environment for teachers. The development of professionalism is the basis for successful personnel management. Continuous training, trainings and professional development support help teachers improve their skills and keep abreast of the latest educational trends[5]. Motivation and encouragement play a key role in stimulating the teaching staff. Tangible and intangible rewards help to increase the enthusiasm and effectiveness of teachers. Effective communication is the basis of a trusting relationship between the administration and teachers. Regular discussions, feedback and openness to dialogue contribute to the effective work of the team. Taking into account the individual needs of each teacher allows you to create conditions for the development of personal potential and increased motivation. The support from the administration in the field of professional growth contributes to the improvement of work results. Performance assessment is a tool to identify strengths and areas for improving the work of educators. Objective assessment criteria help teachers develop and reach new heights. Creating a favorable working environment is the key to

comfortable and productive work of teachers. Well-equipped facilities, support from colleagues and the administration contribute to the success of the school. In general, effective personnel management in schools requires an integrated approach that includes a variety of strategies and methods aimed at supporting and developing the teaching staff. This is the only way to ensure high-quality education and successful functioning of the school.

In the modern world, education has become a key factor in the development of society and shaping the future. In this context, personnel management in schools plays a crucial role in creating an enabling environment for learning and development of both students and teachers. Innovative approaches to personnel management in modern schools are becoming increasingly important for the successful functioning of educational institutions. One of the key innovative approaches is the use of modern information technologies [2]. The introduction of digital tools makes it possible to automate routine tasks, improve communication and information exchange between participants in the educational process. This helps to increase the efficiency of teachers and administration, as well as creates conditions for innovation in teaching. Flexible forms of work also play an important role in modern personnel management. Allowing teachers to work remotely, use flexible schedules, or combine different forms of work helps to increase staff satisfaction and create a more comfortable work environment. Self—organization and self-management is another innovative approach that can change the dynamics of the school team. The transition from a rigid hierarchical structure to a model of self-organization and self-management allows teachers to feel more responsible for their work, which contributes to a more flexible and efficient functioning of the school. Feedback and coaching play an important role in the development of the teaching staff. Systematic feedback helps teachers understand their strengths and areas for improvement, and coaching promotes professional growth and leadership skills development. Innovative teaching methods are necessary for both students and teachers. The use of modern educational techniques helps teachers to be more successful in their work and more effectively transfer knowledge to their students. Creating an inclusive environment is an integral part of innovative HR management [3]. Given the diversity of needs and abilities of each member of the team, it is necessary to create conditions where everyone feels accepted and respected. In general, innovative approaches to personnel management in modern schools are aimed at creating a dynamic and adaptive organization capable of effectively responding to changes and achieving high results in the field of education. The development of innovative strategies in personnel management will help schools to be successful in building the future of education.

Conclusion. In conclusion, effective staff management in schools plays a critical role in providing quality education and creating a supportive educational environment. By increasing professional competence, motivating staff, developing leadership skills and improving communication, personnel management contributes to the successful functioning of the school and the achievement of common goals. The result is not only an increase in the level of education, but also the satisfaction of participants in the educational process, which ultimately contributes to the success of the school as a whole.

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